

A Study on Customer Satisfaction towards Zomato Online Food Ordering with Special Reference to Coimbatore City

Dr. R. Maheswari¹, G. Swarnalatha², Ms. T. Gayathri³

¹Head, ²Assistant Professor, ³PG Scholar

^{1,2,3}Department of Commerce, Dr. SNS Rajalakshmi college of Arts and Science, Putupatti, Tamil Nadu, India

ABSTRACT

Customer satisfaction is a term frequently used in marketing. "In researching satisfaction, firms generally ask customers whether their product or service has met or exceeded expectations". The sample size for the consumer's survey is 150. Tools For Statistical Analysis to Analyze the data and interpret the results by using percentage analysis and ranking. simple Percentage Method, Weighted Average Ranking Method, Chi-Square test. To find out the socio-economic status of the respondents. To determine the motivating factor for purchasing the product through Zomato. The management can maintain the positive attitude of the Customers in order to improve the sales furthermore which in turn to help the company to move towards the better prospects.

How to cite this paper: Dr. R. Maheswari | G. Swarnalatha | Ms. T. Gayathri "A Study on Customer Satisfaction towards Zomato Online Food Ordering with Special Reference to Coimbatore City" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-6, October 2019, pp.683-687, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd29211.pdf>

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

INTRODUCTION

Customer satisfaction is a term frequently used in marketing. It is a measure of how products and services supplied by a company meet or surpass customer expectation. Customer satisfaction is defined as "the number of customers, or percentage of total customers, whose reported experience with a firm, its products, or its services (ratings) exceeds specified satisfaction goals. In a survey of nearly 200 senior marketing managers, 71 percent responded that they found a customer satisfaction metric very useful in managing and monitoring their businesses. "In researching satisfaction, firms generally ask customers whether their product or service has met or exceeded expectations. Thus, expectations are a key factor behind satisfaction. When customers have high expectations and the reality falls short, they will be disappointed and will likely rate their experience as less than satisfying. For this reason, a luxury resort, for example, might receive a lower satisfaction rating than a budget motel even though its facilities and service would be deemed superior in 'absolute' terms."

REVIWE OF LITERATURE:

Sales and Gil, (2018). In the scope of retailing, developed a scale to measure perceived value that the authors denominate PERVAL. This scale is one of the rare attempts to offer an operative proposal of measurement of perceived

value at the point of sale. This proposal represents a step forward in comparison to theoretical approaches The PERVAL scale identifies three basic dimensions of value, that is, emotional value (affective feelings generated by a product), social value (the utility derived from the product's ability to enhance the consumer's social self-concept) and functional value, composed of the sub-dimensions of price (utility derived from the product due to the reduction of its perceived short-term and longer-term costs) and quality (referred to as product performance).

Pathak (2015) entitled "Customer Shopping Behavior among Modern Retail Formats: A Study of Delhi & NCR". The Study was an exploratory research conducted in Delhi & NCR. It specifically focuses on customer shopping behavior in Indian scenario among the modern retail formats.

Nissanoff (2014) discusses the development of systems to negotiate and optimise issues of trust in online exchange, particularly in eBay. From means of providing and viewing customer feedback on sellers through to the active policing of transactions by eBay, the effort and resources invested in maintaining trust in C2C online exchange is indicative of the difficulties that arise in buyer-seller relations where the conventional bases of trust.

Zachary Soreff(2013) director of sales & marketing at Red Letter Days explains the value of an experiential reward: “Experiences offer a more interactive and tuned-in way of promoting a product which, in turn, allows audiences to become more integrated with the brand. They are a popular tool for sales promotion because we are engaging customers emotionally with the brands by giving them a memory to cherish.”

Tim Bishop (2012) of exhilaration explains that by “aligning your brand with a relevant experience you can help to create a more exciting perception of your business in the customer’s mind.” Exhilaration are experts in providing vouchers for adrenaline experiences such as Ferrari driving, bungee jumping and adventure weekends but also offer less extreme pursuits including spa days and gourmet cruises. “The impact of sending someone over a mountain with nothing but a bit of elastic to hold onto will certainly be a lasting one” he continued, “but not necessarily one that everybody would enjoy.”

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Methodology is a plan of action for a research project and explains in detail how data to be collected and analyzed and presented so that they will provide meaningful information.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The descriptive research is used to identify the satisfaction and expectation of consumer and its impact brand preferences.

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS:

TABLE1TABLE SHOWING TYPE OF FOOD PURCHASE THROUGH ZOMATO

Type of food	Number of respondents	Percentage
North Indian	33	22
South Indian	53	35
Continental	21	14
Deserts	15	10
Pastries	18	12
Beverages	10	7
Total	150	100

Source: primary data collected through questionnaire and analyzed through spss.

Interpretation

It is concluded that **35%** of the respondents said that they choose south indian food to purchase through zomato,**22%** of the respondents said that they choose north indian food,**14%** of the respondents said that they choose continental food,**12%** of the respondents said pastries,**10%** of the respondents said deserts and 7% of the respondents said that they choose beverages food to purchase through zomato.

TABLE2TABLE SHOWING RESPONDENTS PREFERRED MEDIUM TO ORDER FOOD ONLINE

Medium	Number of respondents	Percentage
Mobile App	101	67
Web Browser	49	33
Total	150	100

Source: primary data collected through questionnaire and analyzed through spss.

Interpretation:

It is concluded that **67%** of the respondents said that the preferred medium to order food online is mobile app, **33%** of the respondents said that the preferred medium to order food online web browser.

SAMPLING SIZE

The sample size for the consumer’s survey is 150.

SAMPLING METHOD

The Convenience sampling method was adopted for the study with a sample size of 150 respondents from the customers. Convenience sampling techniques has been used to select the respondents. Sample design is non probability sampling design.

TOOLS FOR STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Analyze the data and interpret the results by using percentage analysis and ranking.

- simple Percentage Method
- Weighted Average Ranking Method
- Chi-Square test

OBJECTIVES:

- To find out the socio-economic status of the respondents.
- To determine the motivating factor for purchasing the product through Zomato

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

- The effort to establish continuity in research through linking the result of a given study with those of another.
- The establishment of some explanatory concept.

TABLE3 TABLE SHOWING OVERALL SATISFACTION ABOUT ONLINE FOOD ORDERING

Opinion	No. of respondents	Percentage
Highly Satisfied	51	34
Satisfied	42	28
Neutral	12	8
Dissatisfied	24	16
Highly Dissatisfied	21	14
Total	150	100

Source: primary data collected through questionnaire and analyzed through spss.

Interpretation

It is inferred that **34%** of the respondents are highly satisfied about online food ordering, **28%** of the respondents are satisfied, **16%** of the respondents are dissatisfied, **14%** of the respondents are highly satisfied and **8%** of the respondents are neutral about online food ordering.

TABLE4 TABLE SHOWING RESPONDENTS FREQUENCY OF ORDERING FOOD ONLINE

Frequency of ordering food	Number of respondents	Percentage
Daily	25	17
Weekly Once	33	22
Fortnightly	62	41
Monthly once	30	20
Total	150	100

Source: primary data collected through questionnaire and analyzed through spss.

Interpretation:

It is concluded that **41%** of the respondents order food fortnightly, **20%** of the respondents order food online monthly once, **22%** of the respondents order food weekly once, **20%** of the respondents order food monthly once and **17%** of the respondents order food daily.

WEIGHTED AVERAGE

WEIGHTED AVERAGE WITH RANKING ANALYSIS TABLE SHOWING PROBLEMS FACED BY RESPONDENTS WHILE ORDERING ONLINE FOOD TABLE 5

Problems	Weighted average					Total	Weighted Average	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1			
Delivery delay	22	20	24	22	62	368/150	2.45	V
	110	80	72	44	62			
Service charges	27	42	35	20	26	474/150	3.16	II
	135	168	105	40	26			
Variety of foods	63	38	18	20	11	572/150	3.81	I
	315	152	54	40	11			
Change in orders	23	23	36	50	18	433/150	2.87	III
	115	92	108	100	18			
Customer service	17	28	33	48	24	416/150	2.77	IV
	85	112	99	96	24			

Source: primary data collected through questionnaire and analyzed through spss.

Interpretation

From the table it is clear that problems while ordering variety of foods ranked first with the weighted average of **3.81**, service charges ranked second with weighted average of **3.16**, change in orders ranked third with weighted average **2.87**, customer service ranked fourth with weighted average of **2.77**, and delivery delay ranked fifth with weighted average **2.45**.

CHISQUARE TEST

1. To find the significant difference between occupation of the respondents and overall satisfaction about online food ordering.

Hypothesis

Null hypothesis: There is no statistical significant difference between occupation of the respondents and overall satisfaction about online food ordering.

Alternate hypothesis: There is statistical significant difference between occupation of the respondents and overall satisfaction about online food ordering.

TABLE6 OCCUPATION OF THE RESPONDENTS * OVERALL SATISFACTION ABOUT ONLINE FOOD ORDERING

Occupation of the respondents	Overall satisfaction about online food ordering					Total
	Highly satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Highly dissatisfied	
Agriculture	3	1	0	0	0	4
Private employee	26	5	5	4	5	45
Government employee	20	16	3	3	9	51
Business people	2	20	4	17	7	50
Total	51	42	12	24	21	150

Source: primary data collected through questionnaire and analyzed through spss.

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	32.079(a)	12	.001
Likelihood Ratio	34.742	12	.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	11.843	1	.001
No of Valid Cases	150		

Level of Significant =5%
 Degree of freedom-(R-1) (C-1)
 (4-1) (5-1) =12
 Table value = 32.079
 Calculated value = 34.742

Interpretation:

Since the Pearson Chi-square value is .001 which is less than the p value 0.05 at 12degrees of freedom, we reject the Null hypothesis. Hence we infer there is a significant difference between occupation of the respondents and overall satisfaction about online food ordering.

2. To find the significant difference between age of the respondents and overall satisfaction about online food ordering

Hypothesis

Null hypothesis: There is no statistical significant difference between age of the respondents and overall satisfaction about online food ordering

Alternate hypothesis: There is statistical significant difference between age of the respondents and overall satisfaction about online food ordering

TABLE7 AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS * OVERALL SATISFACTION ABOUT ONLINE FOOD ORDERING

Age of the respondents	Overall satisfaction about online food ordering					Total
	Highly satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Highly dissatisfied	
Below 20 years	6	12	6	2	3	29
20- 30 years	30	9	0	19	9	67
30-40 years	9	18	4	3	8	42
Above 40 years	6	3	2	0	1	12
Total	51	42	12	24	21	150

Source: primary data collected through questionnaire and analyzed through spss.

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	24.971(a)	12	.013
Likelihood Ratio	28.609	12	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.079	1	.184
N of Valid Cases	150		

Level of Significant =5%
 Degree of freedom-(R-1) (C-1)
 (4-1) (5-1) =12
 Table value = 24.971
 Calculated value = 28.609

Interpretation:

Since the Pearson Chi-square value is .013 which is less than the p value 0.05 at 12degrees of freedom, we reject the Null hypothesis. Hence we infer there is a significant difference between age of the respondents and overall satisfaction about online food ordering.

FINDINGS:

Percentage analysis:

- Most 42% of the respondents said that they agree that advertisement influence online purchase of food..
- Majority 67% of the respondents said that the preferred medium to order food online is mobile app.
- Most 34% of the respondents are highly satisfied about online food ordering
- Most 34% of the respondents are highly satisfied about online food ordering

Weighted Average:

- Problems while ordering variety of foods ranked first with the weighted average of 3.81, service charges ranked second with weighted average of 3.16, change in orders ranked third with weighted average 2.87.
- No minimum order factor ranked first with the weighted average of 3.5, promotions ranked second with weighted average of 3.45, fast delivery ranked third with weighted average 3.29.

Chisquare Test Analysis:

- There is a significant difference between occupation of the respondents and overall satisfaction about online food ordering.
- There is a significant difference between age of the respondents and overall satisfaction about online food ordering.

SUGGESTIONS:

- Advertising plays a very important role in the purchase of a online ordering foods as most Customers are like to purchase because of advertisements.
- As most customers were between the age group of 20-30 years so the company strategies should focus on that age group 20- 30 years.
- The company should focus on giving better quality product as most customers were very brand loyal and were generally satisfied with the product.

CONCLUSION:

The company has to focus on building positive image regarding the product on customer's mind. Satisfied customer will always be the worthy asset to the organisation and thus increasing competitive advantage over the rivalries. In future, researchers could investigate how emotional aspects impact on actual purchase behaviours. The management can maintain the positive attitude of the Customers in order to improve the sales furthermore which in turn to help the company to move towards the better prospects.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Buttle, F. (2004), Customer Relationship Management: concepts and tools, Oxford: Elsevier Butterworth-Heinemann
- [2] Gronroos, C. (1994), "From Marketing Mix to Relationship Marketing: Towards a Paradigm Shift in Marketing", Management Decision, 32 (2), pp. 4-20
- [3] Nissanoff, D. (2006) Future shop. How the new auction culture will revolutionize the way we buy, sell and get the things we really want. New York, the Penguin Press
- [4] Sweeney, J.C. & Soutar, G.N. (2001). Consumer perceived value: The development of a multiple item scale. Journal of Retailing, 77, 203-220.
- [5] Sales, V. & Gil, I. (2007). Valor percibido por el consumidor: Una aplicación en la compra de equipamiento para el hogar. Estudios sobre Consumo. 82, 63-82.

BOOKS

- Philip Kotler, Marketing management. eleventh edition, Pearson Education
- R.S.N. Pillai and Bagavathi, Modern marketing principles and Practices., Second Edition S.chand and Company Ltd, New Delhi.
- Rajan Saxena, Marketing management, Second Edition
- Kottler, Marketing management, Eight edition